

“Let the man know his place!”: Challenging the Patriarchy Embedded in Social Language via Twitter (X)

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Abstract

The patriarchy embedded in the social language is among the toughest obstacles to gender equality since it reproduces the traditional secondary position of women. It is a noteworthy reason why feminist movements have focused on language as a field of struggle in the last decades. One of the positive developments in terms of raising awareness about sexism in language was the widespread use of social media. To show this positive influence of social media, this study takes the “Let the Man Know His Place!” trend (#erkekyerinibilsin) on Twitter (X) in Türkiye as a case study and examines it by applying critical discourse analysis. By placing it within larger socio-historical and political frameworks, the study examines how women in Türkiye challenge the patriarchal patterns entrenched in the social language. It also shows how they use new media channels to give visibility to gender inequalities endorsed by social, religious, and political circles.

Keywords

Women’s movement in Türkiye; linguistic sexism; social media feminism; gendered discourse; critical discourse analysis

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Introduction

Male-dominated language as a form of subtle sexism encompassing unequal and unfair treatment of women reinforces gender inequality by reconstructing the sexist beliefs, gender stereotypes, and status differences between women and men. It appears in many countries including gendered, genderless, and natural gender language systems at the word level, sentence level, and discourse level (Mills, 2002). Since linguistic sexism is ingrained in the written and spoken language as a linguistic habit (Lips, 2020), the occurrence of the male-dominated language is normalized within the socio-cultural contexts. Accordingly, people may employ such sexist language in their daily lives without necessarily being aware of the fact that it perpetuates the established hegemonic masculinity.

Feminists long endeavored to show that language plays a critical role in shaping society's perception along gender lines (Mills and Mullany, 2011). The subordinated power status of women is expressed in the way in which women are spoken of (Lakoff, 1973: 75). Therefore, feminist activism attributes critical importance to language as a field of struggle in curbing gender asymmetries (Cameron, 1992: 3). Such activism as a challenge to male-dominated language has included initiatives such as language reforms in different languages to raise consciousness about producing social change.

The widespread use of the internet has provided a new space for the feminist struggle by contributing to women's presence in digital spaces (Munro, 2013). In this respect, it has generated a new understanding of feminist activism e.g. digital feminist activism. Feminist activists began to engage on social media platforms in networking and organizing to challenge all forms of sexism and patriarchy (Mendes et al., 2018: 236-237). This engagement enabled them to reach large audiences beyond the realm of the feminist community (Clark, 2014: 1110).

By building a bridge between the recent online feminist activism and the aforementioned efforts to challenge the male-dominated language, Turkish women reconstructed the sexist remarks by replacing the "woman" and "women" with "man" within phrases, expressions, and idioms through the hashtag #erkekyerinibilsin.³ The trend, which was initiated to mock the sexist remarks and expressions arising out of the conventional culture within the social language, significantly contributed to raising awareness and visibility of linguistic sexism and discrimination against women. Therefore, this research argues that it challenged the established gender roles and stereotypes, deeply entrenched in patriarchal patterns in the conventional wisdom⁴ of society. Thus, conducting such research is significant in enlightening social hierarchies and sexist perceptions embedded in the daily usage of social language.

Several studies have dealt with digital feminist activism in different feminist-identified issues. The analyses covered various subjects of feminist movements in digital space; rape culture (Mendes et al, 2018: 236-246; Mendes et al, 2019a; Mendes et al, 2019b) gender-based violence (Altınay, 2014; Puente et al, 2019; Linabary et al, 2020), sexism (Clark, 2014; Drüeke and Zobl, 2016; Sebring, 2019), and empowerment (Fotopoulou, 2017). Yet, little attention has been paid to movements seeking to change the linguistic sexism within society by raising awareness. The current study will contribute to the existing literature by showing how feminist linguistic activism is incorporated into digital feminist activism.

³ We can translate this into English as 'man should know his place' or 'let the man know his place.'

⁴ The dictionary definition of conventional wisdom is "generally accepted belief, opinion, judgment, or prediction about a particular matter" in <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/conventional%20wisdom>.

This research utilizes critical discourse analysis (CDA). It engages in revealing both the social-political analyses of text and talk and the hidden power relationships within the society (Dijk, 2017: 26-43). Through the lenses of CDA, we will thematically analyze the most engaged and interacted tweets under the hashtag #erkekyerinibilsin, representing the cognitive perception of gender inequality, gender roles, and stereotypes influenced by the social and communicative contexts. In particular, we will apply Van Dijk's socio-cognitive approach. The socio-cognitive approach regards language use and discourse as social representations and subjective definitions of ideologies, knowledge, attitudes, norms, and values of language users. Since CDA focuses on the discourse-cognition-society triangle, it has the potential to enable the research to reveal cognitively mediated sexist language which shapes/ is shaped by the perception within social and communicative contexts. Therefore, the socio-cognitive approach will provide a convenient framework to analyze the #erkekyerinibilsin trend, which appeared to challenge and reverse the cognitional patterns of the social wisdom reflecting the traditional stereotypes and gender roles as obsolete conventions of the culture maintaining gender inequality.

Against this background, this study will address how women in Türkiye challenge the patriarchal patterns entrenched in the social language of the society, and also how they use new media channels to raise awareness for the women's movement by giving visibility to customary gender inequalities. To this end, it will first address the historical and contemporary overview of the status of women and the women's movement in Türkiye. The overview will be valuable in providing the necessary background to examine the cognitively shaped gender inequality, gender roles, and stereotypes within the Turkish context. Secondly, it will briefly explain the research framework and structure of the analysis where the socio-cognitive approach is clarified to present how it is useful for the main motivations of this research. Finally, the main findings of the analyses of the #erkekyerinibilsin trend will be discussed.

Women in Türkiye: A brief historical overview

The women's movement is a cause striving to challenge the political, cultural, social, and economic structures perpetuating the perceived gender inequality and hierarchical gender relations shaped by patriarchal domination (Antrobus, 2004: 3-4). The agenda and focus of the movements may vary in different national and social-cultural settings. However, it is often directed against all forms of marginalization, separateness, and oppression of women to establish social justice and social change (Horn, 2013: 36). The movement in Türkiye is mainly targeted to class, religion, and domestic role arrangements within the society (Coşar and Onbası, 2008: 326).

The construction of gender roles and women's place in Turkish society has been in constant change and transformation within the consecutive phases of Turkish political history (Sirman, 1989). During the Ottoman period, women's place in social life was traditionally defined by the Shariah codes of the Empire. Accordingly, as second-class citizens women were subordinated within the society. Refrained from social and political life, they were responsible only for household management. However, during the Tanzimat era, concerns regarding women's place in society gained relative visibility and importance along with the modernization and westernization steps of the Empire (Kandiyoti, 1991: 22-47). Progressivists influenced by the modernization steps regarded women's oppression as an obstacle to the Westernization of the Empire (Kuloğlu, 2020: 329). Reforming the position of women was regarded as a prerequisite of civilization (Sirman, 1989: 9). Women started to be constructed as mothers and wives in need of education for the development of society (Sirman, 1989: 9). Women's magazines discussing women's issues have gained enormous attention, especially

in terms of producing consciousness and solidarity among women (Gündüz, 2004). By the late nineteenth century, women also started to engage in heated debates with Islamist and traditionalist men (Tekeli, 2010: 120).

Modernization steps did not affect the Muslim legal code advocating sex segregation and unequal legal treatment; however, it brought about modest reforms including the introduction of women's rights in inheritance, abolishment of female slavery, opening of secondary schools for girls and girls' vocational schools, women access to the university (Anadolu-Okur, 2005: 18). During the second constitutional period (1908-1919), the movement was politicized and debates regarding women's rights became vigorous since women's organizations constituted an important role in the national liberation front in the Balkan Wars and First World War (Akin, 2014). Accordingly, women were admitted to universities in 1914, to the workforce in factories, and to public service in 1915 (Tekeli, 2010). Moreover, polygamy was limited by the Family Act of 1917 (Tekeli, 2010).

After the foundation of the Republic of Türkiye in 1923, the traditional Islamic law of the Ottoman Empire was replaced with secular laws and the 1926 Civil Code (Marshall, 2008). The active mobilization of women during the war of independence has transformed the construction of the gender role and gender identity by the State which was itself in the process of making its own state identity. In addition to being wives and mothers responsible for the household, women were regarded as equal and powerful patriotic citizens of the Republic (Sirman, 1989: 10). Accordingly, as patriotic citizens, women were expected to participate in education and profession for the modernization and Westernization of the Republic while fulfilling their traditional role of household management at the same time.

The 1926 Civil Code recognized the equality of women before the law, forbade polygamy, endorsed civil marriage, allowed the right to initiate divorce proceedings, and provided women to inherit (Arat, 2010: 237). Women's suffrage was granted in local and national elections respectively in 1930 and 1934 (Anadolu-Okur, 2005: 24). Through the radically changed laws, the state characterized the gender relations and ideals of the republican Turkish women who were supposed to behave and dress in accordance with the necessities of the modern and westernized state (White, 2003: 146). However, the civil code has also included articles reflecting the patriarchal conditions of the society such as the head of the family concept designating the traditional gender roles of the society assuming women's dependence on the men as the breadwinner (Arat, 2010: 239).

These steps referred later to as the 'state-supported feminism' (White, 2003: 146) in the literature, were criticized by some scholars because of the top-down manner of the male-dominated State prioritizing women's equality as a national polity (Arat, 2010). In this regard, rights and the new notion of citizenship granted to women were regarded as tools for the evacuation of Islam from the legislative and institutional spheres for the full secularization of social life (Kandiyoti, 1991: 38-39). Kandiyoti (2010: 38) refers to women's rights as the symbolic pawns in the making of the nation-state to distance the republic from Islam and remnants of the Ottoman State. Besides, critical scholars regarded women's emancipation as a tool to transform women within the constraints of class and region for the socio-economic development of the Republic to reinforce the republican patriarchy rather than genuinely interested in liberating women (Kandiyoti, 1991; Arat, 1994; Gündüz, 2004). Despite its authoritarian rigidity, state feminism allowed Turkish women to take their places in all social spheres (White, 2003: 158). This newly constructed gender arrangement of the society informed the gender roles of Turkish women for the next half-century.

During the late 1980s, women started to raise their voices by organizing protests and petition campaigns, to draw attention to women's problems (Sirman, 1989: 21). The issues, including domestic

violence against women, sexual freedom, sexual harassment, opening women's shelters, and women's libraries, were brought into the public and political domain (Berik, 1990). The educated, middle-class women believed that although Kemalist reforms assured women inclusion in the political and economic realm, the patriarchal organization of the society led to the continuation of the women's subjugation to men in the private realm (Arat, 1994b: 102). They sought to restructure the society whereby the patriarchal conditions of the civil code would be amended in a less patriarchal manner (Arat, 1994b: 102). They were also against the constructed traditional roles of women as 'mothers in service' which would not allow women to exist and to be recognized as individuals (Gündüz, 2004: 120). Therefore, the movement in the 1980s symbolized the contestation of culturally determined identities and social gender stereotypes (Gündüz, 2004: 123).

Especially due to the accelerated process of Europeanization and democratization sustained by Türkiye's bid to access the European Union (EU), the endeavors of the women's movement have been responded to with the amendment of the civil code in the 1990s to assure gender equality (Coşar and Onbasi, 2008: 331). The articles that discard the equality of the spouses, such as Article 159, requiring the woman to obtain the permission of her husband to work, and Article 153, requiring the woman to adopt the surname of her husband, were abolished (Gündüz, 2004: 123). Besides, other legal measures expanding gender equality were introduced in 2002 (Gündüz, 2004: 123). For example, one of the articles implying the hierarchical gender structure of the society by referring to the man as the head of the family was abolished.

Despite these developments and progress on the legal ground, women's role in society concerning the ongoing problems stemming from hierarchical gender relations are still present at the societal level. Moreover, the rise of the AKP (Justice and Development Party) from 2002 onwards has signaled a new twist regarding gender relations (Ayata and Tütüncü, 2008: 369). The conservative attitude of the AKP government regarding gender issues has become salient, especially since the victory of the AKP in the 2011 elections (Cindoglu and Unal, 2017: 45). Accordingly, gender identities were re-shaped in accordance with Islamic conservative values. The gender discursive approaches regarding the women's role placing them "separate but equal" (The Guardian, 2014) within the society have revealed the construction of the gender hierarchy by AKP's conservative agenda of regulation of women's lives. Such a stance was legitimized through the religious interpretations of the Islamic values subordinating women (Ozbay and Soybakis, 2020: 6).

Islamic values were influential in shaping 'the appropriate sexual behavior of women' while their sexual purity is regarded as the source of family honor, chastity, and appropriate Muslim identity (Gündüz, 2004: 124). Therefore, it is possible to observe the symbolization of women's bodies as a code of collective, cultural, and religious identity of the society. In sum, the conservative AKP government has aggravated the traditional gender roles, and gender inequality and thereby reinforced the stereotyped gender arrangements which had already existed in Turkish society. It is within this context that the #erkekyerinibilsin movement sparked a challenge to the reinforced gender hierarchical relations embedded within the social wisdom of society.

Research framework and structure of the analysis

As discourse is shaped by cognitive structures, revealing cognitive representations and strategies are valuable to address the production or comprehension of the meaning of discourse. Patriarchal patterns ingrained in the cultural and political dynamics of Turkish society are legitimized and produced through the male-dominated language. This, in return, generates and reinforces gender inequality. Through its critical stance, CDA uncovers the existent inequalities within the society-hidden power relations. It is

the social language that mainly describes the functions of the social structures, which appear as a phenomenon constructing the social reality, therefore CDA offers insights both as a methodology and theoretical framework. CDA reveals the inequalities embedded within social language by offering a critical perspective of discourse analysis. In this regard, we aim to examine the reflections of such cognitive processes in discourse with our case study.

To this end, in particular, Van Dijk's socio-cognitive approach is preferred as a research methodology for discourse analysis. Since it has a particular focus on the socially situated cognitive representations and processes in discursive formation, the socio-cognitive approach will be valuable in uncovering the underlying structures, social representations, contents, and language use in communicative and social situations. One of the main arguments of the approach is that the relations between discourse and society are cognitively mediated (Dijk, 2009: 64). Discourse structures and social structures "can only be related through the mental representations of language users as individuals and as social members" (Dijk, 2009: 64). This is because personal experiences that produce the subjective definitions and perceptions of the communicative situations influence talk and text produced within a particular society (Dijk, 2014: 121-146). Based on this discourse–cognition–society triangle, social representations, socially shared knowledge, power, and domination are reproduced through the discourse (Dijk, 2009: 64). In the same direction, we regard those gender roles, their cognitive frames, and inequalities stemming from those are reproduced by the discursive production of social cognition as well.

Analysis

The Twitter (X)⁵ trend "#erkekyerinibilsin" originated with a tweet "My husband can work if he wants" (@ruqinq, 2020). The post went viral when it was retweeted more than 11,700 times and turned into a means of reconstruction of the well-meaning but chauvinistic remarks and degrading sexist put-downs through the hashtag #erkekyerinibilsin. In this way, Turkish women demonstrated the deeply entrenched patriarchal patterns within the social language as reflections of the conventional wisdom of the society reproducing the unequal power relations between men and women. Hence, the movement contributed considerably to drawing attention and raising awareness of the construction and social communication of the expected pattern of behaviors and asymmetric gender arrangement perpetuating gender inequality with respect to different social spheres.

To analyze the way the movement challenged and addressed the socially constructed and communicated women's role and gender hierarchical arrangement, the present study employs semantic analysis. The analysis will be based on the translations of the tweets produced during the trend of "men should know their place". The focal point of the analysis would be semantics in order to reveal the cognitive frames related to gender roles. Particular emphasis will be given to reflections on the discourse to reveal the relation between the language and the social gender arrangement. The first part of the analysis will focus on the tweets revealing cognitive frames of the social wisdom reflected in the social language related to women's place and role in different social contexts and matters including society and family, household activities, female chastity, domestic violence, and women's access to professional life. Then, the second part will deal with the tweets targeting the political statements and their way of outlining the above-mentioned roles and places of women within different social realms.

⁵ At the time of writing this research, the platform was called Twitter. Later it was named X.

Communicating social wisdom on gender roles

The hashtag #erkekyerinibilsin, which can be translated as 'Let the Man know his place', signifies the reversed expression of 'May women know their place' which is used to imply the secondary position of women within society. In this respect, even the statement used by the trend itself is self-evident in showing women's status conveyed and outlined within the social language. Female users target covert linguistic representations of the subordination of women embedded within the social language, which are produced within the different social contexts in relation to different social phenomena. The sayings signifying the women's unequal status in the family, as well as their designated roles and responsibilities in maintaining households (Kandiyoti, 1977: 72), were among the prominent examples of the target of reconstruction:

"My husband can work if he wants" (@ruqinq, 2020).

"Boys should not be educated, they rather should be trained to serve their wives properly in the future." (@cannisinn, 2020).

"The woman you will marry cares about the rice you cook, not about your diploma" (@Zeynakin91, 2020).

"Will you destroy your family just because of a slap? Such things happen in every marriage. The woman both beats and loves her man" (@cirkinfeminik, 2020).

The reconstructed sayings tweeted by female users demonstrated the everyday usage of sexist remarks as a way to reproduce the hidden power relations within the family, especially with respect to constructed traditional gender role stereotypes. The first tweet above revealed the covert implication that a woman's access to professional life is dependent upon her husband's permission or conformity. A woman's responsibility in managing the household is prioritized over her educational life and professional career within the imposed gender roles. In the same direction, the second tweet reversed the patriarchal approach defending that women have no place in social life and that their duty is limited to the family and to serving men. The gender role stereotypes are revealed further by the reconstruction of the third tweet which is a reference to the stereotypical statement that men will not look at career or professional competencies in the woman they marry but at the ability of the woman in the family, such as cooking.

The constructed responsibility of women on family duty trivializes women's individuality by establishing a hierarchy in gender relations and traditional gender responsibilities deeming women to subordinated status. Such an account reinforces the cognition that 'her career should start and end at home' (Ozbay and Soybakis, 2020: 10). With this respect, the value attributed to the family at the expense of the women's individuality is shown by the last tweet reconstructing the remark usually uttered by the elderly who see the domestic violence perpetrated by men as usual and part of the family institution. In this respect, the discursive persuasion aimed to create consent to domestic violence through cultural legitimation implies the prioritization of the family over women's equality and rights within marriage.

Such a cognitive normalization of domestic violence is also achieved through the utilization of the interpretation of religious texts including the Muslims' Holy Book Qur'an and sayings of Prophet Muhammad, Hadiths. Since religion promotes norms and traditions within specific socioeconomic parameters, it is considerably influential in shaping the specific roles and patterns of behavior within the society (Klingorová and Havlíček, 2015: 2). Thus, religious texts appear as one of the sources of asymmetries of male and female representations reinforcing the inequality and women's subordination ingrained within the language. In this respect, the intersection of gender, language, and religion comes from the fact that devout behavior is often constructed as gendered (Julé, 2005).

Therefore, interpretations of the religious texts were also the point of target:

“You can beat men lightly” (@mariaelenahm, 2020)

“When a wife calls her husband to bed, and he refuses and [as a result] the wife spends the night in anger, then angels curse the husband all night till dawn.” (@8WolfAngel8, 2020)

“Every woman preserves the right to marry up to four husbands.” (@Duyguzeynebb, 2020)

The tweets reconstructing the religious texts above show that the interpretations of the religious texts, social cognition, and social perceptions reinforce each other. The first tweet comes from the following verse of the Sura an-Nisa “...As to those women on whose part ye fear disloyalty and ill-conduct, admonish them (first), (next), refuse to share their beds, (and last) beat them (lightly)...”⁶. Accordingly, domestic violence against women is projected to derive its legitimacy through the literal and patriarchal understanding and interpretations of the religious texts (Ammar, 2007: 516) cultivating the social acknowledgement of the violence against women. The selected excerpt from the translation of the Koran is used to present domestic violence as a justifiable response to the ‘so-called’ misbehavior or disobedience of the wife (Douki, et al, 2003: 165). In this way, while women are constructed as obedient wives, women’s subordination to men is associated with God’s commandment as a way of religious legitimation. Therefore, it is normalized to advise women subjected to violence to forgive their husbands for the sake of family unity, which is regarded as the most important social institution.

Religious texts are also influential in shaping the traditional gender roles and structural relationship between men and women in the family prescribing male domination and leadership. Therefore, religious texts contribute to the socio-cognitively perceived and stereotyped gender roles concerning the family. The second tweet drew attention to the fact that women are also subject to sexual abuse as a form of domestic violence. It comes from a Hadith – prophetic saying – in Sahih Bukhari, one of the collections of Hadiths goes as follows: “When a husband calls his wife to bed, and she refuses and [as a result] the husband spends the night in anger, then angels curse the wife all night till dawn.” (qurananswers.me). The traditional interpretation of the Hadith opens up leeway for denying women’s self-determination and supporting the subjugation and abuse of women.

As another example of challenging the religious texts which are powerful guides for the structural relationships reinforcing the male domination within the marriage, the third tweet reconstructed the third verse of the Sura al Nisa: “...Marry women of your choice, Two or three or four...” (qurananswers.me). The tweet highlighting polygyny in Islam showed that acknowledgement and cultural legitimation of the unequal gender relations within marriage are maintained by the patriarchal and traditional interpretations of the religion. In this way, the unequal status of women with respect to men is ingrained in the general consciousness and socio-cognitive perceptions of society reflected by the social language.

Challenging the political statements on the gender arrangement

The trend also revealed discriminatory political statements on gender identity and imposed gender roles on women in different spheres of life including family, professional, and social life through reconstruction. The reconstructed and reversed utterances of the political actors made it clear that the established social cognition on the asymmetrical gender arrangement as a source of discrimination

⁶ Qur’an Sura 4 (Surat an-nisaa’ ‘women’), aya 134.

against women within Turkish society is manifest in political discourses as well. Therefore, this part of the analysis will focus on how gender roles and gender arrangements are discussed and constructed within the political realm:

"A man who refuses paternity is a half person." (@persephonestt, 2020)

"The most beautiful career of a man is fatherhood." (@Dilekdh24, 2020)

"Men should not laugh in public." (@acarkizii, 2020)

"The man who licks ice cream in the street is immoral." (@GayeSuAkyol, 2020)

The reconstruction of the political statements has shown that the political discourse contributes to the reinforcement and legitimation of male domination and women's subordination within society by limiting the existence of women as individual beings. The first tweet above is the reconstruction of the remarks uttered by President Erdoğan during his speech at Sabahattin Zaim University in İstanbul: "A woman who refuses maternity and gives up housekeeping faces the threats of losing her freedom. She is lacking and is a half [a person] no matter how successful she is in the business world." (Hurriyetdailynews, 2020). The remarks imply that the women's basic concern ought to be mothering rather than professional ambitions. In this respect, women's identity is constructed through their maternity rather than as individuals. Accordingly, motherhood is understood as intrinsic to the adult female identity (Ireland, 1993: 1). The promoted maternal function of women indicates the government's conservative politics towards women (Ayata and Tütüncü, 2008: 378).

The second tweet reconstructs the statements of the then Minister of Health on the family during his visit to one of the hospitals in January 2015: "Mothers have a career in the world that no one else can have. They should not concentrate on pursuing any other career rather than maternity." (Diken.com). Motherhood is constructed as a form of women's professional careers. In this respect, Sancar argues that motherhood gives women legitimate social status within the Turkish culture (Sancar, 2014). Such statements refer to the dominant view of the family shaped by conservative values and traditional gender norms promoting women's roles as wives and mothers while denying gender equality in intimate and socio-economic lives (Engin and Pals, 2018: 393).

The constructed inequality within social spheres is also present in the third tweet above which refers to the speech given by then Deputy Prime Minister Bulent Arınc on protecting moral values and gender roles in Bursa in July 2014: "She [woman] should not laugh loudly in front of all the world and should preserve her decency at all times." (The Guardian, 2014). The statement constructed the hierarchical gendered social order reinforcing the unequal social arrangements. Accordingly, moral values are defined through women's behavior and attitudes in the public sphere. These discriminatory remarks contributed to the reproduction of the unequal social arrangements sustained through language use. His declaration drew wide criticism from women, opposition parties, and non-governmental organizations. Turkish women protested the remarks by posting their pictures on social media while laughing out in public under the hashtag #direnkahaha, which means "resist laughter" in Turkish (Akyel, 2014). Therefore, the statement became the target of reconstruction during the #erkekyerinibilsin movement as well.

The last tweet is also a product of the reconstruction of the discriminatory statements on the gender arrangement regarding the social order and social life of Turkish women. It refers to the statements of the famous Islamist opinion leader and writer Mehmet Şevket Eygi, in his column published in September 2015: "Muslim woman ... do not eat ice cream in the street..." (Milligazete, 2020). The sexist statement described the discriminatory cultural and social expectations for behaviors, traits, and characteristics of women. Women's place within the social spheres is discursively oppressed by such sexist statements showing that Islamist men aim to silence women within the public

spheres by ‘restricting them to their boundaries’. In this respect, moral values and social order became a subject of redefinition by women’s behavior and attitude. Through the emphasis on ‘morality’, cultural legitimation and rationalization were aimed.

The excerpts of the prominent figures of the AKP government including President Erdoğan have shown that the conservative government did follow the patriarchal attitudes on a broad scale influenced by religiosity and political conservatism in shaping gender politics. As Engin and Pals argue, patriarchal values have been increasing since the AKP government, which contributes to promoting religiosity and political conservatism regarding gender attitudes including the political, economic, familial, and educational realm (Engin and Pals, 2018: 385). Therefore, the #erkekyerinibilsin movement was influential in terms of revealing the fact the gender politics followed by the government has reinforced the already socio-cognitively established gender inequality and women’s subordination within the society, as discussed in the first part of this analysis.

The trend attracted considerable attention from the different spheres of society. Within social media, various national celebrities and municipalities supported the trend by tweeting under the hashtag #erkekyerinibilsin (BBC.com). Besides, traditional and online mass media channels give wide space to the reflections of the trend as well. The news and newspaper articles discussing the trend and its repercussions within society have been widely articulated. As a result, the trend, which was initiated within the social media realm, found itself a concrete place within the national agenda-setting. In this way, it became considerably visible by reaching even wider audiences beyond the realm of social media. The reactions within society have shown the influence of the expression of the women’s movement on social media.

Against the backdrop of such political and media popularity of the trend, the government circles have necessitated legitimizing their conservative stance by responding to the trend. One of the most prominent reactions was the criticism raised by the pro-government NGO KADEM, the Women and Democracy Association, whose vice-chair is President Erdoğan’s daughter Sümeyye Erdoğan Bayraktar. She posted the following tweet:

“The existence of women and men in society within justice and equitable standards is based on mutual respect and understanding. The campaign that started as an emphasis on empathy #menshouldknowtheirplace (#erkekleyerinibilsin) has reached a stage where the values we believe in are harmed. We condemn and reject this situation.” (Duvar English, 2020)

The statement has shown that the conservative and patriarchal values promoted and supported by the government resisted the reversal of gender roles even if it was for raising awareness. Moreover, the criticism from the conservative circle revealed the polarization that persisted within Turkish society between conservatives and secularists in gender politics. As Baran (2013) argues, Turkish society is divided by the opposing values and worldviews of the conservative and secular groups. In this respect, gender arrangement in Türkiye became one of the battlegrounds of such ‘cultural wars’.

While the movement largely targeted the government’s stance embodied within the discourses of the party officials as well as the President, the main opposition party Republican People’s Party (CHP) also became a target of criticisms as revealed by the tweet: “We should include a woman to our panel, or it will look bad.” (@MeltemGurle, 2020).⁷ The tweet appeared as the reconstructed version of the criticisms to the poster of the panel with the theme “Being a Woman” organized by the

⁷ Meltem Gürle. (@MeltemGurle). 2020. “Panele bir erkek koymamız lazım, yoksa kötü görünecek.” Twitter. June 5, 2020. <https://twitter.com/MeltemGurle/status/1268952969258700802>.

Kepez Municipality run by the CHP mayor for March 8, International Women's Day. The picture of the five male speakers and a male moderator on the poster was ironically criticized on the grounds that there was not any woman participating in the panel and at least for the image of the panel they should have invited the women speakers. While this kind of criticism gave the implication that they promote gender equality within social contexts, it was subject to criticism on the grounds that it also accommodated the male-dominated language presenting women as having only a supplementary role within the social spheres. We observe that even the criticism targeting inequality and discrimination against women accommodates a patriarchal characteristic in itself.

All in all, the trend showed that women's subordination is in question in both the political and social realms of Türkiye. The established gender hierarchy within the society is maintained by different ways of discursive persuasion often through employing religious and cultural legitimation and rationalization. By reversing the sexist remarks embedded within the conventional wisdom of the society, Turkish women drew attention to the phrases, expressions, and idioms as the discursive production of cognitive frames and social cognition reinforcing the traditional gender roles and entrenched gender inequality.

Conclusion

The considerable rise of social media platforms has opened up a space for online feminist activism in recent years. Thanks to such a growing trend providing a space to dialogue and network, women often engage with each other through the usage of hashtags to challenge various forms of gender oppression in their society. As a form of such oppression, linguistic sexism, through which gender inequality is discursively reinforced within the conventional wisdom of society, appears as one of the critical fields of women's struggle in revealing the gender hierarchy and women's subordination. The addressed trend incorporated online feminist activism with linguistic feminism by sparking off the deconstruction of the sexist remarks, patterns, and expressions widely used by Turkish society.

By discursively analyzing and expounding the posts shared during the addressed social media trend, this study crystallizes how the language in use supports and maintains gender inequality and male domination in Turkish society. The performed analysis also finds out that the inequality is not only reinforced by the conventional wisdom through built-in idioms and sayings but is also endorsed and to a broad extent supported by the discourses of the leading figures of the political party in power. As the other noteworthy result, the study shows that social media channels provide women with new opportunities to challenge patriarchal patterns and male domination. As a remarkable one of these, they enable the cause of the women's movement to gain nationwide visibility through their connections to and transitivity with the mass media. This visibility even compels important social and to some extent political, actors to express an opinion on the issue, as is the case in this trend.

By and large, our research contributes to the relevant literature by focusing on online activism to challenge gender inequality in Turkish society. We believe that further research on this issue within both different contexts and different methodological frameworks may expand and deepen our understanding of the transaction between social media and the women's movement.

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